

On Collatz conjecture

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Abstract

The two calculations of Collatz conjecture are as follows.

(1). If a number is odd, triple it and add one.

(2). If a number is even, divide it by two.

If a number is odd, the calculation (1) above is performed first, then the calculation (2) above is executed consecutively after the calculation (1) as the result number of the calculation (1) is always even.

In this paper, the successive calculations of (1) and (2) are treated as a single set of calculations and this one set of calculations, referred to as “the set of calculations”. When an odd number before the set of calculations is denoted as $2n + 1$, the number after the set of calculations is $3n + 2$.

So the number after the set of calculations is greater than the odd number before the set of calculations.

If the number after this set of calculations is odd again, you can perform this set of calculations once more, and the number after the next set of calculations will become even larger. Starting with an original odd number, you can repeat the set of calculations as long as the result is an odd number, causing the original odd number to increase progressively.

In this proof paper, we define a set of calculations as successful if the resulting number from the set of calculations is odd.

We consider how many times the set of calculations can be repeated; in other words, how large the original odd number can become.

We perform the first set calculations on original odd number sequence. Then, we exclude even numbers from the second-level sequence, which consists of the numbers resulting from the set of calculations, and create the second-level odd number sequence. This process is repeated as long as odd numbers remain after the set of calculations.

When we take the smallest term that remains after the each set calculations and create a sequence using the original odd numbers corresponding to the smallest term that remains after each set calculations, we obtain the following sequence.

Recurrence relation:

Initial term $a_1 = 3$

Recursive formula: $a_{K+1} = 2a_k + 1$

where k represents the number of successful repetitions of the set of calculations

The general term of this sequence is expressed as follows:

$$a_n = 2^n - 1$$

($n = k+1$, where k represents the number of successful repetitions of the set of calculations)

The sequence above is a sequence of Mersenne numbers.

Because this sequence diverges to infinity, Collatz conjecture does not hold.

(You can repeat the set calculations to infinity.)

1 Proof

<Proof that the above sequence is developed by the repetition of the set of calculations >

To make the proof easier to understand, we will use the following notation.

Let O represents “odd number”.

When O (odd number) is described as $2n + 1$, we call n is the constituent element number of O and denoted as (n) .

For example, the (n) for 3 is (1), the (n) for 5 is (2), the (n) for 7 is (3)...

For the odd number sequence starting with 3, the sequence of (n) corresponding to the odd numbers is the sequence of natural numbers.

O	3	5	7	9	11
(n)	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)

Definition of the set of calculations

As described in abstract, the definition of the set of calculations is as follows.

The two calculations of Collatz conjecture are as follows.

- (1). If a number is odd, triple it and add one.
- (2). If a number is even, divide it by two.

If a number is odd, the calculation (1) above is performed first, then the calculation (2) above is executed consecutively after the calculation (1) as the result number of the calculation (1) is always even.

In this paper, the successive calculations of (1) and (2) are treated as a single set of calculations and this one set of calculations, referred to as “ the set of calculations ” .

In this proof paper, we define a set of calculations as successful if the resulting number from the set of calculations is odd.

(If the resulting number from the set of calculations is even, the set of calculations are considered unsuccessful.)

We perform the first set of calculations on the original odd number sequence, then exclude even numbers from the resulting sequence (which consists of numbers obtained from the set of calculations), and create a new odd number sequence. We repeat this process as long as odd numbers remain after each set of calculations.

(n) for an odd number determines the success of the set of calculations

let O be an odd number before the set of calculations.

Let N_{after} be the number after the set of calculations.

$$O = 2n+1$$

$$A_{after} = \frac{3(2n+1)+1}{2} = \frac{6n+4}{2} = 3n + 2$$

Since $A_{after} = 3n + 2$, when n is odd, A_{after} is odd, and when n is even, A_{after} is even.

Therefore, if the value of (n) for an odd number O before the set of calculations is odd, the number after the set of calculations (A_{after}) will be odd, and the set of calculations will be successful. Therefore, the value of (n) for an odd number O before the set of calculations is odd, which means that the set of calculations will be successful in that round. If the value of (n) for an odd number O before the set of calculations is even, the result of the set of calculations will be unsuccessful. Therefore, the value of (n) for an odd number O before the set of calculations is even, which means that the set of calculations will be unsuccessful in that round, and A_{after} will be excluded from the odd number sequence results from the set of calculations of that round.

A set of calculations is performed on the odd number sequence in each round. If the value of (n) for a number resulting from the set of calculations is odd, this number remains in the next level odd number sequence for the next set of calculations. if the value of (n) for a number resulting from the set of calculations is even, this number is excluded from the next level odd number sequence for the next set of calculations. The next set of calculations is performed on the remaining (non-excluded) odd numbers. For the first set of calculations, the value of (n) before the set of calculations is the value of (n) for the original odd numbers, so the terms with even value of (n) are excluded from the second level odd number sequence for the second set of calculations.

The original odd number sequence is an odd number sequence that contains all the odd numbers except 1 (that is, an odd number sequence starting from 3).

A part of the state before and after the first set of calculations is shown in the diagram below.

*E indicates that the number is excluded from the set of calculations.

**An odd number and its (n) are displayed in pairs like 3(1).

$13(6) \text{ —————} >E$
 $15(7) \text{ —————} >23(11)$
 $17(8) \text{ —————} >E$
 \vdots

Before the first set of calculations, the value of (n) for original odd numbers alternate between odd and even. Starting from 3, every other odd number remains, and half of these are eligible for the first set of calculations success. (starting from 5, every other odd number with an even value of (n) is excluded.)

We investigate the value of (n) for an odd number before the set of calculations and the value of (n) for the corresponding odd number after the set of calculations, regarding odd numbers that remain after the set of calculations.

Let an odd number before the set of calculations be O_{before} .

Let an odd number after the set of calculations be O_{after} .

$$O_{before} = 2n + 1$$

$$O_{after} = 3n + 2 = 2(n + \frac{(n+1)}{2}) + 1$$

Let $O_{after} = 2N + 1$, then $N = n + \frac{(n+1)}{2}$

Therefore, if the value of (n) for O_{after} is expressed using (n) for O_{before} as n, then the value of (n) for $O_{after} = n + \frac{(n+1)}{2}$. For example, if the value of (n) for O_{before} is 1, then $1 + \frac{(1+1)}{2} = 2$, so the value of (n) for O_{after} is 2. $3(1) \text{ —} >5(2)$ If the value of (n) for O_{before} is 3, then $3 + \frac{(3+1)}{2} = 5$, so the value of (n) for O_{after} is 5. $7(3) \text{ —} >11(5)$

Difference in the value of (n) between adjacent odd numbers

The difference in the value of (n) between adjacent odd numbers before the first set of calculations is 1.

The sequence of the values of (n) corresponding to the original odd number sequence is a sequence of natural numbers, alternating between odd and even. Therefore, starting from 3, every other odd number remains after the first set of calculations. Starting from 5, every other odd number with an even value of (n) is excluded in the first set of calculations. The difference in the value of (n) for adjacent original odd numbers which will remain in the first set of calculations is 2 (The difference between adjacent natural numbers is 1, and every other number is excluded. Therefore, the difference in the value of (n) for the odd numbers that will remain after the first set of calculations is $1+1=2$).

Let “the difference in the value of (n) for adjacent original odd numbers which will remain after the first set of calculations” be D.

As described before, if the value of (n) for O_{after} is expressed using (n) for O_{before} as n, then the value of (n) for $O_{after} = n + \frac{(n+1)}{2}$.

Let the value of (n) for O_{after} of smaller adjacent odd number represent $n + \frac{(n+1)}{2}$.

The value of (n) for O_{after} of bigger adjacent odd number = $(n+D) + \frac{(n+D)+1}{2}$, as the value of (n) for O_{after} of bigger adjacent odd number is $n+D$.

Therefore, the difference of adjacent odd numbers after the set of calculations is as follows.

$$((n + D) + \frac{(n+D)+1}{2}) - (n + \frac{n+1}{2}) = D + D/2$$

Let the difference in the value of (n) for adjacent original odd numbers before the set of calculations be represented as d. $d = D/2$, as D is the difference after the set of calculations (every other term is excluded after the set of calculations).

Therefore, $D + D/2 = 2d + d = 3d$.

The difference in the value of (n) between the adjacent terms remaining after the set of calculations is three times the difference in the value of d between the adjacent terms before the set of calculations.

The difference in the value of (n) between the adjacent terms before the first set of calculations is 1.

$$3d = 3 \times 1 = 3$$

The difference in the value of (n) between the adjacent terms after the first set of calculations is 3.

The first term remaining after the first set of calculations is 5(2). $(3(1) \text{ — first set of calculations —} >5(2))$ In the second-level odd number sequence, which is the sequence of odd numbers remaining after the first set of calculations, the difference in the value of (n) between adjacent numbers is 3. As a result, the value of (n) in the second-level sequence alternate between even

and odd. Therefore, in the second set of calculations, every other term of this sequence is excluded.

The state up to the second set of calculations is shown in the diagram below.

As d after the set of calculations is three times larger than d before the set of calculations ($d_{after} = 3 \times d_{before}$), in general, for the k^{th} set of calculations, 3^k is the difference in the value of (n) between adjacent terms after the set of calculations. Therefore, in each subsequent set of calculations, the value of (n) for remaining odd numbers alternates between even, and odd and every other term is eliminated after the set of calculations.

The first term remaining after the set of calculations

We investigate the first term of the odd number sequence remaining after the set of calculations.

Let the value of (n) for the first term remaining after the set of calculations be n_1 .

Let the value of (n) for the second term remaining after the first set of calculations be n_2 .

In the first set of calculations, the original odd numbers with an even value of (n) are excluded.

The sequence of the values of (n) in the original odd numbers is a sequence of natural numbers, and every other term of the original odd number sequence is removed after the first set of calculations.

Therefore, the relationship between n_1 and n_2 is;

$$\begin{aligned} n_2 &= 2n_1 + 1 \\ n_1 &= \frac{n_2 - 1}{2} \end{aligned}$$

Then, the difference between n_1 and n_2 is;

$$\begin{aligned} n_2 - n_1 &= n_2 - \frac{n_2 - 1}{2} \\ &= \frac{n_2 + 1}{2} \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, as previously mentioned, if the value of (n) for O_{after} is expressed using (n) for O_{before} as n, then the value of (n) for $O_{after} = n + \frac{(n+1)}{2}$.

So the difference between the value of (n) for O_{after} and the value of (n) for O_{before} is;

$$n + \frac{n+1}{2} - n = \frac{n+1}{2}$$

Here, in the next set of calculations (in the second set of calculations), the value of (n) for the second term remaining after the first set of calculations is the value of (n) for O_{before} in the second set of calculations.

So, in the second set of calculations, the difference between the value of (n) for O_{after} and the value of (n) for O_{before} regarding the second term remaining after the first set of calculations is;

$$\frac{n_2 + 1}{2}$$

Hence, the difference between the value of (n) for the first term and the value of (n) for the second term remaining after the first set of calculations is the same as the increase in the second set of calculations for the second term after the first calculations.

Since the value of (n) for the first term after the first set of calculations is 2, which is an even number, it is excluded from the second set of calculations, and the second term, whose value of (n) is 5, becomes the first term remaining after the second set of calculations.

The increase in the value of (n) for this term in the second set of calculations is the same as the difference between the value of (n) for the first term and the value of (n) for the second term remaining after the first set of calculations.

As previously mentioned, the difference between the terms after the set of calculations is 3^k (k is k^{th} set of calculations). In the first calculations k = 1, so the difference between the terms after the set of calculations is $3^1 = 3$. The value of (n) for the first

term after the first set of calculations is 2 (an even number), and the (n) for the second term after the first set of calculations is an odd number ($5 = 2+3$).

Similarly, for the nth set of calculations, the value of (n) for the first term after the n^{th} set of calculations is an even number because the value of (n) for the second term at the previous level is always an odd number. Additionally the value of (n) for the first term after the n^{th} set of calculations is 3^K bigger than the value of (n) for the second term at the previous level.

So, the first term is always excluded from the set of calculations at the next stage, and the second term remains at the next stage, as the value of (n) for the second term is 3^K bigger than the value of (n) for the value of (n) for the first term.

Therefore, each time the set of calculations is repeated, if you take the original odd number (before the first set of calculations) corresponding to the first term remaining after the set of calculations, the original odd number you take becomes (the previous original odd number you took) $\times 2 + 1$

Summary and conclusion

Let the sequence of the first odd numbers be defined as the first-level sequence. The sequence obtained as a result of the first set of calculations is termed the second-level sequence. Continuing in this manner, the sequence formed by the remaining terms after the k-th set of calculations is referred to as the (k+1)-level sequence.

1. The initial sequence is an odd sequence starting from 3.
 2. The sequence of the values of (n) in this odd number sequence is a sequence of natural numbers.
 3. If the value of (n) for a term of a sequence before the set of calculations is even, the term does not remain in the sequence after the set of calculations (i.e., the next level sequence).
 4. Since the sequence of (n) values in the sequence before the first set of calculations is a sequence of natural numbers, with odd and even numbers alternating, every other term from the initial sequence remains in the second-level sequence after the first set of calculations.
 5. The difference between the (n)-values of adjacent terms after the set of calculations is three times the difference between the (n)-values of adjacent terms before the set of calculations. (3d difference)
 6. The difference between the (n)-values of terms in the second-level sequence after the first set of calculations is $1 \times 3=3$. Therefore, the difference between the (n)-values of terms in the second-level sequence is 3, an odd number. Since the (n)-values in the second-level sequence alternate between odd and even, every other term from the sequence before the second set of calculations remains in the third-level sequence after the second set of calculations.
 7. In subsequent sets of calculations, the difference between the (n)-values of terms in the sequence after the calculations is three times the difference between the (n)-values of terms in the sequence before the calculations. Therefore, the (n)-values of the next level sequence alternate between odd and even, resulting in every other term from the previous level sequence remaining in the next level sequence.
- Term Remaining Process:
8. The initial term of the second-level sequence after the first set of calculations is 5, and its (n)-value is 2 ($* 3(1) \rightarrow 5(2)$). Since the (n)-value 2 of this initial term 5 in the second-level sequence is even, it is excluded in the second set of calculations and does not appear in the third-level sequence.
 9. In subsequent sets of calculations, the difference between the (n)-values of adjacent terms in the sequence before the calculations and the difference between the (n)-values of the initial term before the calculations and its corresponding term after the calculations will be the same value. That is, the difference between the (n)-values of the initial term before the calculations and its corresponding term after the calculations is 3^k . Therefore, the initial term of the previous level sequence is excluded in the next level sequence, and the second term of the previous level sequence becomes the initial term of the next level sequence. As the sets of calculations progress, the initial term changes to different terms (corresponding to different terms in the original odd number sequence).
 10. Since half of the terms from the previous level sequence always remain in the next level sequence after each set of calculations, the sets of calculations can be continued indefinitely.
 11. With each set of calculations performed, the original first-level odd number corresponding to the remaining terms becomes increasingly larger (the set of calculations transforms the original number into a larger number).
 12. As the set calculations progress, the initial term of the previous level sequence is excluded and every other term remains in the next sequence. Therefore, (the value of the term in the original odd number sequence corresponding to the initial term of the next level sequence) = $2 \times$ (the value of the term in the original odd number sequence corresponding to the initial term of the previous level sequence)+1.

Therefore, each time the set calculations is repeated, if you take the original odd number (prior to the first set calculations)

corresponding to the first term remaining after the set of calculations, the original odd number you take becomes (the previous original odd number you took) $\times 2 + 1$.

The sequence developed in this manner is as follows.

Recurrence relation:

Initial term $a_1 = 3$

Recursive formula: $a_{K+1} = 2a_k + 1$

where k represents the number of successful repetitions of the set of calculations

The general term of this sequence is expressed as follows:

$$a_n = 2^n - 1$$

($n = k+1$, where k represents the number of successful repetitions of the set of calculations)

The sequence above is a sequence of Mersenne numbers.

Because this sequence diverges to infinity, Collatz conjecture does not hold.

(You can repeat the set calculations to infinity.)

2 Illustration

A part of the sequence of numbers that change after the first and second set of calculations is shown in the figure below. This figure is helpful for understanding what is described in the proof section more easily.

Numbers with an even value of (n) are excluded from the set of calculations.

Numbers with an odd value of (n) remain as successful set of calculations and proceed to the next stage.

In the first set of calculations, every other odd number starting from 3 remains, while every other odd number starting from 5 is excluded.

In the odd numbers remaining after the first set of calculations, the difference in the value of (n) between adjacent terms is the first power of 3, or 3. Therefore, the value of (n) in the sequence of odd numbers remaining after the first set of calculations (the second-level sequence) alternates between even and odd.

In the second set of calculations, every other term is excluded in the same way as in the first set of calculations.

The difference in the value of (n) between adjacent terms remaining after the second set of calculations is 3^2 , so the value of (n) alternates between even and odd.

Generally, in the k^{th} set of calculations, the difference in the value of (n) between adjacent terms remaining after k^{th} set of calculations is 3^k , so the value of (n) alternates between even and odd at every level.

Also, the value of (n) for the first term of the odd number sequence remaining after a set of calculations is an even number. This is because the difference in the value of (n) between the term before the set of calculations and the term after the set of calculations is the same as the difference in the value of (n) between adjacent terms after the previous set of calculations, which is 3^k times (the value of (n)). The difference of 3^k times (the value of (n)) changes the value of (n) from odd to even after the

set of calculations. As the value of (n) becomes even, this term is excluded from the next set of calculations. Each time the set of calculations proceeds, every other odd number starting from the first term remaining in the previous step is excluded. (Since the first term is excluded in the next set of calculations, the first term remaining always changes from the previous level.) Every other number with an odd value of (n) starting from the second term remains in the next set of calculations. So, half of the numbers from the previous step are excluded and half of numbers remain.

References

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